

Comment on “Application of the extended Lie group analysis to the Hopf functional formulation of the Burgers equation” [J. Math. Phys. 54, 072901 (2013)]

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The quest to find new statistical symmetries in the theory of turbulence is an ongoing research endeavor which is still in its beginning and exploratory stage. In our comment we show that the recently performed study of Waławczyk and Oberlack [J. Math. Phys. **54**, 072901 (2013)] failed to present such new statistical symmetries. Despite their existence within a functional Fourier space of the statistical Burgers equation, they all can be reduced to the classical and well-known symmetries of the underlying deterministic Burgers equation itself, except for one symmetry, but which, as we will demonstrate, is only a mathematical artefact without any physical meaning. Moreover, we show that the proposed connection between the translation invariance of the multi-point moments and a symmetry transformation associated to a certain invariant solution of the inviscid functional Burgers equation is invalid. In general, their study constructs and discusses new particular solutions of the functional Burgers equation without referring them to the well-established general solution. Finally, we also see a shortcoming in the presented methodology as being too restricted to construct a complete set of Lie point symmetries for functional equations. In particular, for the considered Burgers equation essential symmetries are not captured.

I. THE NEW STATISTICAL SYMMETRIES AND THEIR DETERMINISTIC ORIGIN

In Ref. 1, a set of three particular *statistical* symmetries was derived to “find new and more general invariant solutions” [p. 1] of the functional Burgers equation in Fourier space. These are

$$S_1: \quad \bar{k} = k, \quad \bar{t} = t e^{c_1 \epsilon}, \quad \bar{z} = z e^{c_1 \epsilon}, \quad \bar{\Phi} = \Phi, \quad (1)$$

$$S_2: \quad \bar{k} = k, \quad \bar{t} = t + c_1 \epsilon, \quad \bar{z} = z e^{c_2 k \epsilon}, \quad \bar{\Phi} = \Phi, \quad (2)$$

$$S_3: \quad \bar{k} = k, \quad \bar{t} = t, \quad \bar{z} = z + \epsilon \delta(k), \quad \bar{\Phi} = \Phi, \quad (3)$$

presented in Ref. 1 as Eqs. [89-91], [132-134], and [86-88], respectively, where the first symmetry S_1 is only admitted in the inviscid case $\mu = 0$. To discuss their link to the underlying *deterministic* Burgers equation in the infinite domain, it is helpful to recapitulate all equations and notions involved. Using the symbolic notation of Ref. 1, which in turn has been taken from Ref. 2, the deterministic Burgers equation in physical space is denoted as

$$\frac{\partial u(x,t)}{\partial t} = -u(x,t) \frac{\partial u(x,t)}{\partial x} + \mu \frac{\partial^2 u(x,t)}{\partial x^2}, \quad (4)$$

and in Fourier space as (Eq. [36]¹)

$$\frac{\partial \hat{v}(k,t)}{\partial t} = i \int k'' \hat{v}(k',t) \hat{v}(k'',t) dk' - \mu k^2 \hat{v}(k,t), \quad (5)$$

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where $k'' = k - k'$, and, where u and \hat{v} are the velocity fields in physical and wavenumber space, respectively, connected by the 1D Fourier transform³

$$\hat{v}(k, t) = \int dx e^{ikx} u(x, t), \quad (6)$$

where \hat{v} then carries the physical dimension $[\hat{v}] = L^2/T$, if u carries the dimension of velocity $[u] = L/T$. By coarse graining or averaging equations (4) and (5) to yield the corresponding statistical equations for the continuously sampled probability distribution functionals $P([u(x)], t)$ and $P([\hat{v}(k)], t)$, one obtains, according to Ref. 2, the following statistical evolution equations, respectively:

$$\frac{\partial \Phi([y(x)], t)}{\partial t} = i \int y(x') \lim_{x'' \rightarrow x'} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \frac{\delta^2 \Phi([y(x)], t)}{\delta y(x') \delta y(x'')} dx' + \mu \int y(x') \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} \frac{\delta \Phi([y(x)], t)}{\delta y(x')} dx', \quad (7)$$

and (Eq. [37]¹)

$$\frac{\partial \Phi([z(k)], t)}{\partial t} = \int k'' z(k' + k'') \frac{\delta^2 \Phi([z(k)], t)}{\delta z(k') \delta z(k'')} dk' dk'' - \mu \int k'^2 z(k') \frac{\delta \Phi([z(k)], t)}{\delta z(k')} dk', \quad (8)$$

where instead of the probability distributions P the associated characteristic or moment-generating functionals Φ are considered. Their connection is given through the functional Fourier transforms (acting as path integrals)

$$\Phi([y(x)], t) = \int P([u(x)], t) e^{i(y, u)} \mathcal{D}u(x), \quad (9)$$

and

$$\Phi([z(k)], t) = \int P([\hat{v}(k)], t) e^{-i[z, \hat{v}]} \mathcal{D}\hat{v}(k), \quad (10)$$

where (y, u) denotes the dimensionless scalar product of real vector fields

$$(y, u) = \int dx y(x) \cdot u(x), \quad (11)$$

and $[z, \hat{v}]$ its associated Hermitian form for complex vector fields

$$[z, \hat{v}] = \int dk z(k) \cdot \hat{v}^*(k). \quad (12)$$

Note that while on the one side the fields $y(x)$ and $z(k)$ were initially introduced as auxiliary fields to generate all moments of the probability distribution functionals P , they can also be identified in each time step t as complementary to the physically sampled fields $u(x)$ and $\hat{v}(k)$, respectively.⁴ Here, the latter symbols $u = u(x)$ and $\hat{v} = \hat{v}(k)$ denote in each space a collection (ensemble) of all admissible vector fields realized by the flow. Hence, both ensembles of fields $y = y(x)$ and $z = z(k)$ are explicitly time-independent, yet carrying the physical dimensions $[y] = T/L^2$ and $[z] = T/L$ due to the dimensionless bilinear forms (11) and (12). However, they are not arbitrary fields, since, by construction, they must vanish (like their complementary fields u and \hat{v}) sufficiently fast at infinity in either space.⁵ The complex field $z(k)$ is further to be restricted by $z^*(k) = z(-k)$. Finally, both fields are connected by the complementary 1D Fourier transform

$$z(k) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int dx e^{ikx} y(x), \quad (13)$$

which then, along with the corresponding Fourier transform (6) for the ensemble of sampled fields $u(x)$ and $\hat{v}(k)$, results to the invariant relation $(y, u) = [z, \hat{v}]$.

Now we are ready to show that the statistical symmetry \mathcal{S}_1 (1) emerges from the well-known deterministic scaling symmetry^{6,7}

$$\mathcal{S}_1^D : \quad \bar{t} = t e^{c_1 \epsilon}, \quad \bar{x} = x, \quad \bar{u} = u e^{-c_1 \epsilon}, \quad c_1 \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (14)$$

of the inviscid ($\mu = 0$) Burgers equation (4). The connection is easily established, if we ensure that in *any* transformed domain we always have a consistently defined Fourier transform in all spaces: Since x in \mathbb{S}_1^D (14) transforms invariantly, its complementary variable k will transform accordingly: $\bar{k} = k$. Hence, according to (6), the sampled wavenumber field transforms exactly as the sampled velocity field: $\bar{\delta} = e^{-c_1\epsilon} \hat{\delta}$. Then, according to (10), its complementary field can only transform as $\bar{z} = e^{c_1\epsilon} z$, which finally results to the functional symmetry \mathbb{S}_1 (1) admitted by (8). Unfortunately, this issue has not been discussed in Ref. 1, thus creating the misleading impression that (1) is a new statistical symmetry.

Similarly with the statistical symmetry \mathbb{S}_2 (2), which basically follows from the deterministic translation symmetry for the coordinates of the Burgers equation (4):

$$\mathbb{S}_2^D: \quad \bar{t} = t + c_1\epsilon, \quad \bar{x} = x + ic_2^*\epsilon, \quad \bar{u} = u, \quad c_2 \in \mathbb{C}, \quad (15)$$

since again, according to (6), the transformations of x and u induce the complementary transformations $\bar{k} = k$ and $\bar{\delta} = e^{-c_2^*k\epsilon} \hat{\delta}$, which then, according to (10) with its Hermitian form (12), results to $\bar{z} = e^{c_2k\epsilon} z$ as given in (2). Although this symmetry has been correctly recognized in Ref. 1 as “the Fourier transform of the usual translation group” [p. 16] for the complementary field $\bar{y}(x + \epsilon) = y(x)$ on the statistical level, it, however, has not been recognized that this link is even further rooted down to the deterministic level (15), if $c_2 = i$. Note that c_2 can only take on pure imaginary values, otherwise the constraint $z^*(k) = z(-k)$ is not satisfied in the transformed domain, i.e., transformation (15) is therefore ultimately a translation symmetry of real numbers.

At first sight it seems that the third symmetry \mathbb{S}_3 (3) might be of a different type, in that it represents a unique statistical symmetry which is not linked to an underlying deterministic symmetry of the Burgers equation. Although this observation is correct, by closer inspection, however, it turns out to be deceptive. The reason is that this statistical symmetry cannot be linked to a deterministic variable transformation of *any* kind or type, neither to a distinctive symmetry, nor to any ordinary transformation. To be more precise, it effectively can only be linked to an identity or null transformation on the deterministic level: Since symmetry (3) only consists of a shift in z , its complementary deterministic variable $\hat{\delta}$ thus must transform invariantly $\bar{\delta} = \hat{\delta}$ in order to warrant, according to (10) and (12), a consistent functional Fourier transform in the transformed domain. Hence, all variables $(t, x, k; u, \hat{\delta})$ defining the deterministic state of the system stay unchanged. This obviously violates the classical principle of cause and effect, simply as no cause at all exists from which (3) can emerge as a symmetry transformation (see also Ref. 8). Symmetry \mathbb{S}_3 (3) is therefore unphysical. Additionally, it shows a transformational inconsistency when transferring this symmetry to physical space, where, according to (13), it has a non-diverging and thus well-defined but non-invariant representation

$$\mathbb{S}_3: \quad \bar{x} = x, \quad \bar{t} = t, \quad \bar{y}(\bar{x}) = y(x) + \epsilon, \quad \bar{\Phi}([\bar{y}(\bar{x})], \bar{t}) = \Phi([y(x)], t). \quad (16)$$

Although being a trivial symmetry of its associated equation (8) in wavenumber space, transformation (16) is not admitted as a symmetry anymore by the corresponding functional Burgers equation (7) in physical space. The reason for this is obvious: Underlying functional equation (7) is not autonomous in y to admit a translation symmetry as (16) in this variable. Hence, apart from being unphysical, symmetry \mathbb{S}_3 (3) is also a mathematical artefact of equation (8) only. Note that this problem of admitting unphysical statistical symmetries is not typical for the statistical Burgers equation only, it essentially exists for any statistical equation which emerges from an underlying deterministic theory, as we have already shown for all statistical formulations of the Euler and Navier-Stokes equations (for more details, see Refs. 8–10).

II. ON \mathbb{S}_1 AND ITS NON-CONNECTEDNESS TO THE TRANSLATION INVARIANCE OF THE MULTI-POINT MOMENTS

In Ref. 1, it is shown that the scaling symmetry \mathbb{S}_1 (1) induces the following invariant function (Eq. [107]):

$$\Phi([z(k)], t) = e^{C_1 + C_2 + \dots + C_n + \dots}, \quad (17)$$

with

$$C_1 = \frac{1}{t} \int dk f_1(k)z(k), \quad C_2 = \frac{1}{t^2} \int dk dk' f_2(k, k')z(k')z(k-k'), \quad \dots \quad (18)$$

where all the f_i are arbitrary complex valued functions. However, in order for Φ (17) to be a *solution* of the underlying inviscid ($\mu = 0$) functional Burgers equation (8), the f_i has to satisfy the (unclosed) relations (shown here only up to second order $n \leq 2$, Eqs. [113] and [114])

$$f_1(k) = -k \int dk' f_2(k, k') - \frac{1}{2}k \int dk' f_1(k-k')f_1(k'), \quad (19)$$

$$f_2(k, k') = -\frac{1}{2}k' \int dk'' [f_3(k, k'-k'', k'') + f_3(k, k-k', k'') + f_3(k, k'', k-k')] \\ - \frac{1}{2}k' \int dk'' f_1(k'') [f_2(k-k'', k'-k'') + f_2(k-k'', k-k')], \quad (20)$$

along with two other restrictions, Eqs. [108] and [111], to satisfy the natural physical constraints $z^*(k) = z(-k)$, $\Phi^*([z(k)], t) = \Phi([-z(k)], t)$, and $|\Phi([z(k)], t)| \leq 1$. Note that Eq. [114] in Ref. 1 was derived incorrectly¹¹ and that it needs to be replaced by the correct result (20). Then, by introducing the following (uncoupled) transformations (Eqs. [118-121]):

$$\bar{f}_1(k) = f_1(k) + c_1 t \delta(k), \quad \bar{f}_2(k, k') = f_2(k, k') + c_2 t^2 \delta(k) \delta(k'), \quad \dots \quad (21)$$

it is argued in Ref. 1 that these would induce the translation invariance of the multi-point moments given through Eqs. [122-128]. Their argument is that, since transformations (21) for the arbitrary functions f_i leave the invariant function Φ (17) unchanged¹², i.e., since the transformations (21) are admitted by the moment generating functional Φ (17) as symmetry transformations, they will naturally induce an invariance in the statistics of the multi-point moments when only generated by that invariantly mapped field $\bar{\Phi} = \Phi$. This statement is correct as long as the conditions for that statement are correct. But this is not the case here: Although function Φ (17) itself stays invariant under transformations (21), its conditions (19) and (20), however, in order to be a solution of the statistical Burgers equation (8), do *not* stay invariant as can be readily verified. In other words, transformations (21) induce different solution-constraints than given by (19) and (20), but yet for the very same function Φ (17), since, by construction, it stays invariant under this transformation process. That means, although this function gets invariantly mapped into itself, it is no longer a solution to the underlying statistical equation anymore, simply because the constraints are no longer fulfilled. Hence, the proposed transformation (21) cannot be regarded as a symmetry transformation which maps solutions to new solutions; it is just some arbitrary transformation which only leaves the function Φ (17) invariant, nothing more. Consequently, the conclusion in Ref. 1, namely, that (21) induces a translation invariance in the statistics of the multi-point moments, is invalid.

III. FINAL REMARKS

R1. In the process of solving the symmetry determining equations in Ref. 1 (Eqs. [41-47]), only three symmetries, namely, S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 (1)-(3) were determined. Unfortunately, the all-important Galilean invariance, e.g., in the form of a pure Galilean boost

$$S_4: \quad \bar{k} = k, \quad \bar{t} = t, \quad \bar{z} = e^{ikt} \epsilon_z, \quad \bar{\Phi} = e^{-iz(0)\epsilon} \Phi, \quad (22)$$

with its infinitesimal solutions $\xi_t = 0$, $\xi_k = ikt z(k)$, and $\eta = -iz(0)\Phi$, was not found.¹³ Note that when making use of the extra but *not* necessary assumption $z(0) = \int z(k)\delta(k)dk = 0$, all functional derivatives first have to be carried out before evaluating at this point, i.e., $[\delta z(0)/\delta z(k)]_{z(0)=0} = \delta(k) \neq 0$.

R2. In our opinion, when studying particular solutions of the functional Burgers equation (8), as was done throughout Ref. 1, it is essential to refer these to the well-known general solution already given in Ref. 2 by Eq. [38]²

$$\Phi([z(k)], t) = \int e^{-i[z, T^t \hat{v}_0]} P([\hat{v}_0(k)]) \mathcal{D}\hat{v}_0(k), \quad (23)$$

where $P([\hat{v}_0(k)])$ is the probability distribution of the given initial field \hat{v}_0 at time $t = 0$, and where T^t is the deterministic semi-group operator of the flow. Since this operator $T^t \hat{v}_0(k) = \hat{v}(k, t)$ is explicitly determinable for the Burgers equation (4) in physical space via the Cole-Hopf transformation,¹⁴ the above general solution (23) can be expressed in a closed form. The flow is given as¹⁵

$$T^t \hat{v}_0(k) = -2\mu \int dx e^{ikx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \ln \varphi(x, t), \quad (24)$$

with

$$\varphi(x, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi\mu t}} \int dx' \exp \left[-\frac{(x-x')^2}{4\mu t} - \frac{1}{2\mu} \int_0^{x'} dx'' u_0(x'') \right], \quad (25)$$

where $u_0(x)$ is the corresponding given initial field in physical space. An interesting investigation in Ref. 1 would have been to show if the two presented invariant solutions, Eqs. [107] and [141], can be found in (23) as asymptotic solutions living on some dynamical attractor, or whether they are just particular solutions belonging to a specifically chosen initial condition depending on the choice of the arbitrary integration functions f_i . How to analytically and numerically calculate a path integral such as (23) is, e.g., discussed in Ref. 16.

R3. A shortcoming of Ref. 1 is the applied method to find general Lie point symmetries of functional equations. As laid down in Sec. [II.C], the method is only capable to generate a very restricted set of symmetries, since the independent variable k (or x in physical space) is treated as an unchangeable quantity which should stay invariant $\bar{k} = k$ under any transformation. The reason for this approach is given in their preceding study of Ref. 17, in stating that “ x [or k] is not transformed in the present approach since it constitutes a continuous “counting” parameter, such as a summation index in the classical counterpart” [p. 604]. However, such a restriction is not justified and will only lead to a very restricted set of symmetries. Although k and x emerge as continuous counting indices when infinitely smoothing the underlying discrete system to a continuous system, this limiting coarse-graining process nevertheless turns the dimensionless discrete indices into variables carrying a physical dimension, which, at least, must already allow for a (re-)scaling and thus for a transformation in the units. A more general transformation is then ruled by the Jacobian in each space: $d\bar{k} = |J_k| dk$, and $d\bar{x} = |J_x| dx$. Hence, the variables k and x should be *included* into the transformation process, otherwise essential symmetries will be missed. For example, when considering the functional Burgers equation (8), or (7), the method in Ref. 1 obviously misses out on several essential symmetries, e.g., as

$$\mathbf{S}_5: \quad \bar{k} = e^{-\epsilon} k, \quad \bar{t} = e^{2\epsilon} t, \quad \bar{z} = e^\epsilon z, \quad \bar{\Phi} = \Phi, \quad (26)$$

$$\mathbf{S}_6: \quad \bar{x} = \frac{x}{1-\epsilon t}, \quad \bar{t} = \frac{t}{1-\epsilon t}, \quad \bar{y} = y, \quad \bar{\Phi} = \Phi, \quad (27)$$

where \mathbf{S}_5 is a scaling and \mathbf{S}_6 a projective symmetry,¹⁸ both for the viscous ($\mu \neq 0$) as well as for the inviscid case ($\mu = 0$). Note that for determining the above symmetries, \mathbf{S}_5 and \mathbf{S}_6 , it was not necessary to employ the full functional Lie group machinery as done in Ref. 1. Since the complete set of Lie-point symmetries for the deterministic Burgers equation (4) are known,⁶ it is only necessary to proceed as in Sec. I in the beginning of this comment to obtain all corresponding symmetries in functional space.¹⁹

R4. Finally, we want to point out some technical mistakes in Ref. 1: (i) The form of the intermediate result Eq. [40] is incorrect, since the evaluation of Eq. [39] leads to a determining integral equation with different kernel dimensions in each term, and not to a differential equation as given by Eq. [40]. The inconsistency in the shown indices clearly indicates this. (ii) The first three terms in Eq. [46] have the wrong (effective) sign. Instead of (+ + -) it should be (- - +). (iii) The statement that the assumption $z(0) = 0$ “was also made by Hopf [in Ref. 2] in the case of the Navier-Stokes equations and corresponds to the zero mean velocity in the domain” [p. 7] is incorrect and misleading, since in Ref. 2 no such correspondence was made. Instead, the assumption of a zero mean velocity field $\int dx u(x, t) = 0$ is only connected to the restriction $\hat{v}(0) = 0$ of the velocity’s Fourier field $\hat{v}(k)$ and not to the restriction $z(0) = 0$ of the auxiliary field $z(k)$ [see p. 103-104 in Ref. 2]. The latter restriction $z(0) = 0$ only arises in the context of finding converging

solutions [see first footnote on p. 122 in Ref. 2], and thus has no relation to the assumption of a zero mean velocity field. Hence, interpreting the translation symmetry $\bar{z}(k) = z(k) + \epsilon\delta(k)$ (Eq. [87]¹) as a shift of zero-gradient mean-fields is incorrect and not justified.

- ¹ M. Waławczyk and M. Oberlack, “Application of the extended Lie group analysis to the Hopf functional formulation of the Burgers equation,” *J. Math. Phys.* **54**, 072901 (2013).
- ² E. Hopf, “Statistical hydromechanics and functional calculus,” *J. Ration. Mech. Anal.* **1**, 87–123 (1952).
- ³ In Ref. 2 the Fourier transform is defined oppositely than in Ref. 1. As a result, the respective equations in Ref. 1 and Ref. 2, corresponding to (5) and (10), only differ by their sign in the imaginary unit.
- ⁴ Note that in Ref. 1 the sampled values for u are denoted by v ; here, however, we stay with the notation from Ref. 2.
- ⁵ For the Euler and Navier-Stokes equations, the fields $y(x)$ and $z(k)$ must be additionally solenoidal, i.e., $\nabla \cdot y = 0$ and $k \cdot z = 0$, in order to eliminate the pressure field in each case; for the 1D Burgers equation, however, this restriction is of course irrelevant.
- ⁶ P. J. Olver, *Applications of Lie Groups to Differential Equations*, 2nd ed. (Springer, Verlag, 1993).
- ⁷ I. L. Freire, “A note on ‘Lie symmetries of inviscid Burgers equation,’ ” *Adv. Appl. Clifford Algebras* **22**, 297–300 (2012).
- ⁸ M. Frewer, G. Khujadze, and H. Foysi, “Comment on ‘Statistical symmetries of the Lundgren-Monin-Novikov hierarchy,’ ” *Phys. Rev. E* **92**, 067001 (2015).
- ⁹ M. Frewer, G. Khujadze, and H. Foysi, “On the physical inconsistency of a new statistical scaling symmetry in incompressible Navier-Stokes turbulence,” e-print [arXiv:1412.3061](https://arxiv.org/abs/1412.3061) (2014).
- ¹⁰ M. Frewer, G. Khujadze, and H. Foysi, “A critical examination of the statistical symmetries admitted by the Lundgren-Monin-Novikov hierarchy of unconfined turbulence,” e-print [arXiv:1412.6949](https://arxiv.org/abs/1412.6949) (2014).
- ¹¹ The error in Eq. [114] in Ref. 1 also has an effect on the subsequent solution given by Eqs. [129–131].
- ¹² Under the additional assumption that $z(0) = z(k)|_{k=0} = 0$.
- ¹³ However, note that ultimately the Galilean invariance (22) is not compatible with the underlying constraint of a time-independent z -field, which basically is a defining condition of the functional Burgers equation (8), and which, of course, must hold in the transformed domain as well in order to warrant an overall consistent symmetry analysis of this equation. That means, since the Galilean symmetry (22) does not induce the necessary constraint $\partial_t \bar{z} = 0$ in the transformed domain from $\partial_t z = 0$, and vice versa, the presence of this constraint ultimately breaks the Galilean symmetry (22). Unfortunately, this symmetry breaking mechanism of the underlying constraints $\partial_t y(x) = 0$ and $\partial_t z(k) = 0$ of the corresponding functional Burgers equations (7) and (8), has not been taken into account or discussed in Ref. 1.
- ¹⁴ J. Kevorkian and J. D. Cole, *Multiple Scale and Singular Perturbation Methods* (Springer, Verlag, 1996).
- ¹⁵ M. Rosenblatt, “Scale renormalization and random solutions of the Burgers equation,” *J. Appl. Probab.* **24**, 328–338 (1987).
- ¹⁶ I. Hosokawa and K. Yamamoto, “Numerical study of the Burgers’ model of turbulence based on the characteristic functional formalism,” *Phys. Fluids* **13**, 1683–1692 (1970).
- ¹⁷ M. Oberlack and M. Waławczyk, “On the extension of Lie group analysis to functional differential equations,” *Arch. Mech.* **58**, 597–618 (2006).
- ¹⁸ Note that: (i) For scaling symmetry \mathbb{S}_5 the functional derivative $\delta/\delta z = \partial/(\partial z dk)$ transforms invariantly. (ii) The projective symmetry \mathbb{S}_6 only exists in physical space as its underlying deterministic symmetry is ill-defined in Fourier space.
- ¹⁹ However, note again that ultimately also symmetry \mathbb{S}_6 gets broken by the underlying constraint $\partial_t y(x) = 0$ of the functional Burgers equation (7), in the same way as explained in Ref. 13.